

**A MULTIMODAL APPROACH FOR PAIN MODULATION AND PAIN INTENSITY
REDUCTION IN INDIVIDUAL WITH LATERAL EPICONDYLITIS AND ASSOCIATED
NON-SPECIFIC NECK PAIN**

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ABSTRACT

Background: Lateral Epicondylitis (tennis elbow) is a common musculoskeletal condition causing elbow pain and functional limitation. It is often associated with Non-Specific Neck Pain due to biomechanical links between the cervical spine and upper limb. Multimodal physiotherapy approaches targeting both proximal and distal structures may improve treatment outcomes. **Objective:** To evaluate the effectiveness of a multimodal physiotherapy approach—including the Tyler Twist technique, inhibition–ischemic compression, proximal kinetic chain exercises, and conventional therapy—in reducing pain and improving function in individuals with lateral epicondylitis associated with non-specific neck pain. **Methodology:** A randomized Clinical Trial was conducted on participants aged 30–40 years with lateral epicondylitis and non-specific neck pain. Subjects were divided into two groups: **Group A** received the Tyler Twist technique, inhibition–ischemic compression technique and conventional therapy; **Group B** received proximal kinetic chain exercises, inhibition-ischemic compression technique and conventional therapy; Outcomes were measured using NPRS, PRTEE, NDI, grip strength, MMT, and MFDS. Data were analysed using paired t- test. **Results:** Both experimental groups showed significant improvements in pain, strength, and function Group B demonstrated the greatest improvement in pain reduction, grip strength, and cervical disability scores. **Conclusion:** Multimodal physiotherapy is effective in managing lateral epicondylitis associated with non-specific neck pain. Proximal kinetic chain exercises showed superior benefits, highlighting the importance of including proximal strengthening in rehabilitation programs.

KEYWORDS: Lateral epicondylitis, non-specific neck pain, multimodal physiotherapy, proximal kinetic chain exercises.

INTRODUCTION

The elbow joint is a highly intricate structure that acts as a key mechanical connection between the shoulder, wrist, and hand in the upper limb and plays a vital role in positioning the hand for precise movements, enabling strong gripping actions, and functioning as a pivot point for the forearm, any Impairment or loss of elbow function can greatly hinder the performance of everyday tasks.^[1] Repetitive movements of wrist and forearm often lead to overuse injuries, of which lateral epicondylitis is most prevalent. Lateral Epicondylitis (LE) sometimes known as "tennis elbow," is one of the most prevalent repetitive strain injuries affecting the upper limb.^[2] It is

an injury caused by repeated stress on the extensor muscles of the forearm in which the muscle that is anatomically implicated is extensor carpi radialis brevis (ECRB).^[3] The brachioradialis, extensor carpi radialis, supinator, extensor digitorum, and extensor carpi ulnaris are the wrist extensors that are typically observed to be painful in patients with lateral epicondylitis.^[4] Musculoskeletal pain rarely occurs in isolation within a single joint or region; instead, dysfunction and discomfort often manifest across interconnected anatomical areas.^[5] Clinically, it is frequently observed that individuals diagnosed with lateral epicondylitis (LE), commonly known as "tennis elbow," also

experience non-specific neck pain(NSNP), the simultaneous presence of these conditions poses diagnostic and therapeutic challenges due to regional interdependence, neurophysiological interactions, and shared biomechanical or sensorimotor adaptations.^[6]

Nonspecific painful conditions in the cervical spine are frequently the source of referred pain in the lateral elbow region.^[7] Nonspecific neck pain (NSNP) can be described as pain in the side area of the neck that extends to the superior border of the clavicle and the suprasternal notch, as well as from the superior nuchal line to the scapular spine.^[8] This is also accompanied by soreness and tenderness in the trapezius muscle.^[9] Therefore, implementing a comprehensive, multimodal rehabilitation approach that addresses both the affected tendon and the related proximal regions may lead to enhanced pain relief, improved function, and better overall pain modulation.^[10]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design: Randomized Clinical Trial

Study setting: Clinical Outpatient Setting

Study Population: Patients from the Amritsar region of India who met the inclusion criteria for Lateral epicondylitis and Nonspecific neck pain were chosen.

Sampling method: Participants were selected using purposive sampling and then randomly allocated into two groups.

Sample size: Patients between the ages of 30 and 40 who had Lateral epicondylitis and Nonspecific neck pain,

with a sample size of 72 determined using the G-power version 3.1.9.4 were considered for the study.

Inclusion criteria

- Age: 30–40 years old
- Gender: Male/Female
- Soreness and pain close to or on the lateral epicondyle for 1.5 month
- Pain and discomfort localized to the neck region for 1.5 month
- Trigger points in trapezius muscle
- A positive lateral epicondylitis test:
 1. Refused to extend the middle finger
 2. Reduced strength of grip
 3. Resisted actively extending the wrist

Exclusion criteria

- Prior shoulder and elbow injuries within past 1 year
- Rheumatological illness history
- Injection as a component of their medical treatment within the past 3 months
- Cervical spondylosis, spondylolisthesis, and specific neck dysfunction
- Spurling test, cervical compression, ULTT, and other positive tests for cervical radiculopathy
- Active lifestyle following gym
- Any history of physiotherapy in the last 6 months
- Any specific acquired or congenital conditions related to cervical spine

Variables

Dependent variables	Demographic variables	Independent variable
NPRS	Age	Tyler twist technique, conventional treatment
Grip Strength Dynamometer	Gender	Inhibition – ischemic compression technique
Patient rated tennis elbow evaluation	Height, weight	Proximal kinetic chain exercises
Neck disability index	BMI	
Myofascial diagnostic scale		
Manual Muscle Testing		

Instruments and tools

- Weighing machine
- Measuring tape
- Dynamometer
- Flexbar (Yellow, Red)
- Patient rated tennis elbow evaluation scale
- Neck disability index
- Numerical pain rating scale (NPRS)
- Myofascial diagnostic scale
- Manual muscle testing grading system by David J. Magee

Outcome measures

- Muscle strength
- Pain and functional limitations related to lateral

epicondylitis

- Neck disability
- Pain intensity
- Presence and severity of myofascial trigger points

Procedure: Patients were divided randomly into two groups:

- Group A
- Group B

Group A: Participants in Group A received the Tyler Twist technique, inhibition–ischemic compression technique for trigger points of the trapezius muscle, and conventional treatment (UST).

Group B: Participants in Group B received Proximal kinetic chain exercises, inhibition–ischemic compression

technique for trigger points of the trapezius muscle, and conventional treatment (UST).

Protocol: The total frequency and duration of treatment were four sessions per week, each lasting 20–30 minutes, for a total of six weeks.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Within-Group Comparison of Outcome Measures in Group A.

Outcome Measure	Pre (Mean ± SD)	Post (Mean ± SD)	t-value	P-value
1. NPRS Score	5.61 ± 0.69	3.12 ± 0.60	21.965	<0.001**
2. PRTEE Score	54.94 ± 6.50	31.94 ± 6.08	18.306	<0.001**
3. Grip Strength	24.81 ± 4.99	34.06 ± 6.15	-13.009	<0.001**
4. NDI Score	24.69 ± 2.62	8.24 ± 2.94	29.750	<0.001**
5. MFDS Score	10.75 ± 0.81	3.15 ± 1.06	35.954	<0.001**
6. MMT Score	3.61 ± 0.49	4.12 ± 0.33	-5.488	<0.001**

Group A demonstrated statistically significant improvements in all outcome measures following the intervention. There was a marked reduction in pain intensity as indicated by the decrease in NPRS scores ($t = 21.965$, $p < 0.001$). Functional disability also improved significantly, with PRTEE and NDI scores showing substantial reductions ($p < 0.001$). Grip strength and

muscle strength (MMT) increased significantly, indicating enhanced muscular performance. Similarly, MFDS scores decreased, reflecting improved functional status. Overall, the intervention applied in Group A was effective in reducing pain and disability while improving strength and function.

Table 2: Within-Group Comparison of Outcome Measures in Group B.

Outcome Measure	Pre (Mean ± SD)	Post (Mean ± SD)	t-value	P-value
1. NPRS Score	6.22 ± 0.87	2.06 ± 0.80	28.020	<0.001**
2. PRTEE Score	55.72 ± 6.29	23.28 ± 6.43	27.625	<0.001**
3. Grip Strength	25.56 ± 5.59	40.03 ± 8.38	-17.961	<0.001**
4. NDI Score	25.42 ± 4.59	7.66 ± 2.36	21.055	<0.001**
5. MFDS Score	11.47 ± 1.77	2.59 ± 1.04	25.404	<0.001**
6. MMT Score	3.53 ± 0.51	4.88 ± 0.34	-13.876	<0.001**

Group B showed highly significant improvements across all outcome measures, with greater magnitude compared to Group A. Pain levels (NPRS) decreased significantly ($t = 28.020$, $p < 0.001$), while functional outcomes such as PRTEE and NDI scores demonstrated substantial improvement. Grip strength showed a marked increase ($t = -17.961$, $p < 0.001$), indicating better recovery of hand function. Additionally, MFDS scores significantly decreased and MMT scores increased, reflecting enhanced muscle strength and functional capacity. These findings suggest that the intervention used in Group B was more effective in improving overall clinical outcomes.

DISCUSSION

The present study aimed to assess the effectiveness of a multimodal physiotherapy approach in reducing pain intensity and enhancing functional outcomes in individuals with lateral epicondylitis associated with non-specific neck pain. The intervention protocol comprised Tyler Twist eccentric exercises, the inhibition–ischemic compression technique, proximal kinetic chain (PKC) exercises, and conventional physiotherapy. This comprehensive approach was intended to target both the local pathology at the lateral elbow and the proximal biomechanical dysfunctions that may contribute to persistent symptoms.

The findings of the study indicated that both groups demonstrated improvements in pain intensity, grip strength, functional performance, neck disability, and trigger point sensitivity following the intervention period. However, the extent of improvement differed between the groups. The most significant improvements were observed in Group B, which received the multimodal intervention including proximal kinetic chain exercises. In contrast, Group A, which underwent the Tyler Twist technique, inhibition–ischemic compression technique, and conventional therapy, showed moderate improvement.

The greater improvement seen in Group B underscores the importance of incorporating the entire upper limb kinetic chain into rehabilitation. Proximal stability of the scapula and shoulder plays a crucial role in facilitating efficient distal mobility, optimizing force transmission, and enhancing neuromuscular coordination, thereby leading to improved treatment outcomes.^[11] The PKC exercises implemented in this study specifically targeted key scapular stabilizers such as the serratus anterior, middle trapezius, and lower trapezius, as these muscles are essential for maintaining proper scapular alignment and providing a stable base for upper limb movements.^[12] When scapular stability is compromised, abnormal movement patterns can develop, increasing mechanical stress on the elbow joint and wrist extensor tendons. Strengthening these proximal muscles likely

improved scapular control and force distribution across the upper limb in Group B, thereby reducing stress on the lateral epicondyle.^[11]

These findings support the concept of regional interdependence, which suggests that dysfunction in one anatomical region can influence symptoms in another. Kibler et al. (2013) highlighted the role of scapular stability in maintaining optimal upper limb function and preventing excessive stress on distal joints. Similarly, Struyf et al. (2013) reported that dysfunction of the scapular muscles can significantly contribute to upper limb pain and functional limitations.^[13]

Improvements in grip strength were also most pronounced in Group B, likely due to enhanced proximal stability contributing to better distal performance. In Group A, the observed improvements may be attributed to the inclusion of eccentric loading through the Tyler Twist technique. Eccentric training is widely recognized as an effective intervention for tendinopathies, as it promotes tendon remodelling by stimulating collagen synthesis, improving fibre alignment, and increasing tensile strength.^[14] Tyler et al. (2010) demonstrated that eccentric loading using a flexible bar significantly reduces pain and enhances functional outcomes in individuals with chronic lateral epicondylitis, likely due to improved neuromuscular control and reduced tendon neovascularization.

Overall, the results of this study clearly indicate that Group B exhibited the greatest improvements across all outcome measures, including pain intensity, grip strength, functional performance, neck disability, and trigger point sensitivity. These findings highlight the effectiveness of integrating eccentric tendon loading, myofascial trigger point management, and proximal kinetic chain strengthening in the rehabilitation of individuals with lateral epicondylitis associated with non-specific neck pain.

This study supports the implementation of a multimodal physiotherapy approach that addresses both distal and proximal components of the upper limb kinetic chain. Such an approach may result in greater pain reduction, improved functional outcomes, and enhanced overall recovery in individuals with lateral epicondylitis accompanied by cervical dysfunction.

CONCLUSION

Multimodal physiotherapy is effective in managing lateral epicondylitis associated with non-specific neck pain. Proximal kinetic chain exercises showed superior benefits, highlighting the importance of including proximal strengthening in rehabilitation programs.

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ETHICAL APPROVAL

A written informed consent was obtained from the patient, and study was performed with approval of ethical committee at Khalsa College Amritsar . Ref No IEC/KCA/PT/2025/25, Date :- 6-02-2026